

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine

VOLUME 2
ISSUE 21 APRIL-JUNE ISSUE
A QUARTERLY PUBLICATION

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume II, Issue II | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

REYNES L. SUMAYLO

Instructor III

West Visayas State University-Calinig Campus

sumaylo.reynes@wvsu.edu.ph

“A HEART THAT BEGS TO FORGET”

I want to have amnesia,
to erase the face of him;
to forget he broke this foolish heart,
and made my brighter mornings dim.

I want to have amnesia,
to forget my own mistakes;
to bury scenes I should not keep,
and all the hurtful words that ache.

I want to have amnesia,
so love will leave my chest;
to block the feelings calling him,
and give my tired heart its rest.

I want to have amnesia,
so burdens fade like rain;
to be a whole person again,
and walk away from pain.